

4. Accurate observations of plants and lines are possible because selection was made only from combinations of highly productive populations.

This technique has been applied to develop high-yielding varieties since 1983 and two new high-yielding rice varieties, Toenonbyeo 2 and Pyongyang 24, were developed successfully.

The mean yield of Toenonbyeo 2, in comparative tests from 1992 to 1994, was 9,475 kg ha⁻¹, outyielding the check by 1,852 kg ha⁻¹. The yield of this variety, under conditions of no-fertilizer application in 1995, was 8,101 kg ha⁻¹ in Rakrang District, where soil fertility is high. Its record yield under experi-

Germination rate (%) of three varieties under low-temperature conditions at Pyongyang in 1995.

Variety	Treatment 1 ^a			Treatment 2 ^b		
	6 d	12 d	18 d	3 d	6 d	9 d
Pyongyang 24	80	98	100	90	92	91
Yomju 1 (tolerant check 1)	12	96	100	100	100	100
Olbyeo 1 (tolerant check 2)	10	78	82	91	98	100

^a15/10 °C day/night temperature. ^b30/25 °C day/night temperature.

mental conditions was 11,706 kg ha⁻¹ with 120 kg ha⁻¹ of applied N.

The mean yield of Pyongyang 24 for 3 tests from 1993 to 1995 was 8,732 kg ha⁻¹, which was 1,873 kg ha⁻¹ higher than that of the check. This variety showed high yield under conditions of low-fertilizer application. It yielded

7,650 kg ha⁻¹ in 1995 in the demonstration plot in Sariwon City, with the application of 200 kg ha⁻¹ of ammonium sulfate. Its highest recorded experimental yield was 11,282 kg ha⁻¹. Pyongyang 24 is also highly tolerant of cold (see table). ■

Yield stability analysis of rice hybrids

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The stability of some promising rice hybrids released for yield and yield components (panicles plant⁻¹, spikelets panicle⁻¹, fertility, and grain weight) was studied at Mandya, Bangalore, Shimoga, Kathalagere, and Brahmavar in Karnataka. These locations represented different agroclimatic zones. Data from the 1994 wet season on five hybrids and four checks were analyzed as per the Eberhart and Russell model.

Highly significant genotype × environment interactions were observed for yield and yield components. No hybrid or check variety showed stability over the environments studied for yield. But all the hybrids showed an average performance with a regression coefficient (*bi*) equal to unity. This was mainly due to instability in the number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ and the degree of fertility.

Even though the regression coefficient deviated from unity, medium-duration hybrid IR58025A / KMR3 (KRH2) was the best performer at all the locations, except Brahmavar in coastal Karnataka. Another short-duration hybrid, IR58025A / IR9761-19-

1R (KRH1), also performed similarly, with a yield much superior to that of checks Rasi and Mangala at all locations except Brahmavar. The results from the correlation analysis between stability parameters (*bi* and *s²di*) for grain yield and yield components indicate that stability parameters in rice hybrids may be governed by different genes and gene interactions. ■

Yield system analysis in rice hybrids

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Grain yield is a complex trait that is influenced by genetically controlled physiological components. The rate of accumulation of biomass and actual yield, as well as the ratio between these two components, can determine a genotype's yielding ability. At a similar level of harvest index, increased grain yield can come from increased total biomass or increased harvest index, or increased biomass and harvest index. We therefore investigated the physiological and genetic causes of the yield superiority in rice hybrids in the 1994 wet season.

The test materials involved eight rice hybrids belonging to different maturity groups, their A, B, and R parents, and three check varieties—Jaya, IR72, and Tellahamsa. They were grown in three replications using a randomized complete block design. Observations on shoot and root dry weights at different growth stages were recorded on five random and competitive plants in each replication. Grain yield, panicle dry weight, and spikelet fertility were also recorded. Based on the observations, total biomass at different growth stages and harvest index were calculated.

Heterosis over the best check and better parent was calculated and subjected to a test of significance. Only IR58025A / Swarna, PMS3A / PR103, and IR58025A / IR32809 showed significant commercial heterosis for grain yield, total dry matter, and panicle dry weight at harvest despite a negative heterosis for spikelet fertility. These hybrids also showed heterosis for dry matter accumulation at many growth stages. IR58025A / IR52256 and IR62829A / IR53901 showed negative commercial heterosis for grain yield, harvest index, and spikelet fertility with no or very low heterosis for other growth parameters. The negative heterosis for spikelet fertility in all the hybrids clearly indicated a need to improve spikelet fertility in hybrids by

resorting to special breeding to increase restoration ability. The superior yielding ability of the hybrids over the checks was found to come from increased total biomass and increased panicle weight, with almost the same level of harvest index. Harvest index and panicle weight, however, can be further increased by increasing spikelet fertility in hybrids, which can ensure an additional increase in total grain yield. ■

Studying heterosis for grain yield and its components in hybrid rice

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Heterosis in hybrid rice was studied in the 1995 wet season under irrigated conditions. Some 22 F_1 hybrids developed by using cytoplasmic male sterile lines IR58025A, PMS1A, PMS2A, PMS3A, and PMS10A and 18 restorers were grown along with the standard variety HKR126 in a randomized block design with three replications. Each line was planted in a single row 3 m long. Spacing between rows and plants was kept at 30×15 cm. Observations were recorded for grain yield plant^{-1} , panicles plant^{-1} , grains panicle^{-1} , and 1,000-grain weight.

The standard heterosis of F_1 hybrids for these traits was calculated over HKR126. The standard heterosis was found to be significant for all four traits. It was both negative and positive for grain yield plant^{-1} (-0.57 to 54.75%), panicles plant^{-1} (-14.84 to 89.14%), and grains panicle^{-1} (-16.04 to 43.28%), and negative for 1,000-grain weight (-34.55 to -5.82%). Positive and significant standard heterosis was observed in 6 hybrids for grain yield plant^{-1} , in 12 hybrids for panicles plant^{-1} , and in 7 hybrids for grains panicle^{-1} . The hybrids PMS1A / Pusa 44-33 (54.75%), PMS3A / RP2151-40-1 (40.86%), PMS2A / IR 31802-56-4-3-3R (37.37%), IR58025A / IRON89-54 (36.48%),

PMS1A / RP2151-173-1-3 (33.21%), and PMS2A / Pusa 44-33 (32.86%) showed positive and significant standard heterosis for grain yield plant^{-1} , panicles plant^{-1} , and grains panicle^{-1} . ■

Standard heterosis of rice hybrids for yield and yield components

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The exploitation of hybrid vigor is widely recognized as the only readily available means to raise the genetic yield ceiling in areas where yields have already approached their potential. In this approach, developing highly heterotic rice hybrids with superior yield performance and evaluating them across environments are important. We assessed the performance of 10 promising rice hybrids to estimate the standard heterosis over popular medium-duration rice variety Prabhat for yield and yield components.

Significant differences existed among the hybrids for all characters studied, thus indicating considerable variability. Hybrids were of early to medium duration and had a semidwarf plant stature. Six hybrids had significantly higher grain yield over Prabhat. MTUHR2015 had the highest grain yield (5.65 t ha^{-1}), followed by MTUHR2002 (5.13 t ha^{-1}). The released hybrids APHR1 and APHR2 had the 4th and 5th positions, respectively. Though hybrids had long panicles with more spikelets panicle^{-1} , the expected grain yields were not realized because of spikelet sterility and lower grain weight.

The standard heterosis of hybrids for plant height was insignificant except in MTUHR2006, which showed a negative response (-17.8%). Similarly, MTUHR2020 and MTUHR2015 exhibited significant and positive heterosis for panicle length. All hybrids except MTUHR2006 exhibited a very high positive standard heterosis for number

of spikelets panicle^{-1} . This was reflected in the positive high heterosis for grain yield. All hybrids showed negative and significant standard heterosis for 1,000-grain weight because Prabhat had a bold grain with a high 1,000-grain weight of 32 g. Most of the hybrids possessed slender grains with lesser weight.

Heterosis is a highly cross-specific phenomenon. To use heterosis successfully to improve grain yield, parental genotypes need to have a high potential yield. We need to reduce spikelet sterility and increase grain weight to realize the effect of high heterosis for number of spikelets panicle^{-1} in rice hybrids. ■

Developing Pusa 5A, a stable indica CMS line with high outcrossing potential

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From available germplasm and breeding lines at IARI, we have identified Pusa 150-2, a maintainer with excellent agronomic traits. Pusa 150-2 is a high-yielding semidwarf indica variety with excellent grain quality.

When test-crossed with IR58025A, it produced F_1 progeny with 100% pollen sterility. The F_1 progeny was backcrossed to Pusa 150-2 and a population of approximately 750 BC_1 plants was raised. All plants showed 100% pollen sterility under the microscope but segregated for various agronomic characters. Thirty plants showing characters comparable with those of Pusa 150-2 were backcrossed. All the progenies were 100% sterile.

Fifteen of these progenies were selected for further backcrossing. All plants in the BC_3 population showed 100% sterility. Five of these populations showing close similarity to Pusa 150-2 were further backcrossed and the BC_4 population was raised. All five populations showed perfect pollen and